

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not always black in coloration. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear could be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six toes in length. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, however their fur can range from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are some of one of the best at climbing trees. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb trees for protection, meals, and even hibernation. The vast majority of their weight loss plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight loss plan: Their varied weight-reduction plan offers them the ability to reside in a large range of habitats. In addition they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the probably bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their spread-out nature and reduced habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the name of essentially the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt younger mammals such as elk and moose. Their coloration varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder height of 3. Three feet. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than those found within the Rocky Mountains as a consequence of a richer weight loss program. Every year there are 46 attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for his or her aggressive behavior, grizzlies are chargeable for the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are virtually as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight ft lengthy, and 4 toes tall on the shoulder. □□ Eating regimen: Their weight-reduction plan is similar to mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, resulting from more plentiful food sources, the islands can support a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to change into their own subspecies. This has led to a extra complex social structure which results in less battle between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears can be aggressive. Attributable to their isolation, there is only one assault on people every different 12 months. Largest species of bear on this planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is generally made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range in the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 toes tall. They are a threatened species on account of lack of habitat from climate change. Despite their monumental size polar bears may be fast, sustaining a 6 mph pace in the water. □□ Features: In comparison with other bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slim head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Food plan: Their weight loss program consists largely of animals, particularly seals which they can odor from a mile away. Although they appear white, their fur is actually clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears can be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are uncommon due to the remote nature of their habitat. Known for its cream shade chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and often widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered susceptible. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Diet: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses,

fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on people are growing as individuals encroach on their habitat.

□□ Dangerous? They're one of the simplest bears to tame (and due to this fact common in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North [chimpanzee teddy bear](#) American counterparts.

Discovered solely in China. 99% of its weight-reduction plan is bamboo. In truth, the second individual in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while defending his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body.

□□ Location: Pandas are found solely in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 remain in the wild and they're considered a susceptible species.

□□ Dimension: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and might be over four ft tall, a formidable feat considering they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at start. It also has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same pattern in mild brown and white.

□□ Eating regimen: Not like different bears the panda's eating regimen is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo.

□□ Options: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them regular: they poop over 40 occasions a day!

□□ Dangerous? Assaults are uncommon however harmful, provided that pandas have one in every of the highest chew forces of any carnivore.

Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey.

□□ Location: The Solar bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its population is unsure however thought of vulnerable and on the decline as a consequence of lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and different body parts utilized in conventional medicines.

□□ Measurement: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear.

□□ Features: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for their pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that appears like a rising sun. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer.

□□ Weight-reduction plan: Sun bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In reality, they have an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia.

□□ Dangerous? Attributable to its shy nature, assaults are rare. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the name sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants.

□□ Location: The Sloth bear is found in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they're considered weak.

□□ Dimension: They are fifty five to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds.

□□ Features: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're straightforward to inform other than different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they are very quick and may out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws.

□□ Food plan: Their food regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit.

□□ Harmful? They're probably the most aggressive bears, with probably the most attacks on people, mostly as a consequence of surprise encounters. They blow the mud round with huge puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 feet away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not mix well with rhinos and elephants, usually charging at each other when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final quick-faced bear. The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear to be glasses. This vulnerable species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador.

□□ Size: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall.

□□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last brief-confronted bear and the only bear native to South America.

□□ Features: The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that generally appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in timber where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses.

□□ Eating regimen: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a food plan consisting of largely cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they may opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs.

□□ Harmful? Residing in distant mountains, these shy bears would be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear conduct is closer to the polar bear. They feature the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA tests had been unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas will not be bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in space. Most bear assaults occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their own household which can

be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks which will point out a bear is nearby, wherein case you want to be additional vigilant. Listed here are just a few tips you need to use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're right here so they don't by accident startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have nice intentions, a bear is prone to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP).** If you see a bear, do not attempt to approach or feed it. This includes food, but in addition your toiletries, for example. Whichever method you choose, be certain that it is not less than 200 feet away out of your tent so you do not entice bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** When you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make yourself look as huge as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You can too prolong a jacket above your head to make your self look larger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hold them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Speak to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward. 6. **Battle Back.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, do not play dead. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 toes long, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the largest bear by both measurement and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight back with all of your strength and hope that it'll again down. Which bear is essentially the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is thought for essentially the most assaults. When in bear country, it's always sensible to carry bear spray. It's nicely deserved, especially when cubs are round. Every year there are approximately forty six grizzly attacks, 6 leading to dying. In North America, grizzly bears have essentially the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most prone to see an American black bear, on average there is just one assault per year. When it comes to raw chunk power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When utilizing the chew pressure quotient (chew power relative to dimension), the solar bear packs probably the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fireplace but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he became an icon and to today is the star of the longest-running public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear recognized for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous through-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a responsibility-free lifestyle. He additionally might be the primary bear to receive his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada close to where he was from. Chris also wrote How one can Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal parts backpacking food and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic suggestions, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

